

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF SYMBOLS IN INTERNATIONAL ECONOMIC RELATIONS AND BUSINESS CULTURAL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract

Along with other aspects of the cultural environment, the understanding and interpretation of symbols are of key importance in international economic relations and business communication. In the context of modern processes of digitization and overloaded flow of compact informative items, graphic symbols have gained special importance. Their significance and diversification in fact correlate with the civilizational development of mankind. Appearing as a cultural artifact, they are able to unite people across time, countries and continents, performing an anthropological, metalinguistic, communicative function. At the same time, a special role in the cultural and communicative sphere of modern international business is played by globally standardized and generally accepted categories of symbols, which include Universal Coded Character Set (UCS) ISO / IEC 10646, Unicode, emojis, flags and emblems of countries and cities, currency symbols and commercial logotypes. Due to their simple and accessible forms, they are perceived intuitively, appealing to the human subconscious and forming a universal language that is understood by people from all over the world. Forming a global symbolic system of visual images and a common semantic foundation, graphic symbols are able to be better remembered, accelerate the transmission of messages, broadcast the same meanings, knowledge, ideas, feelings, emotions, ideas and values within the planetary cultural-communicative space.

Keywords: cross-cultural communication, cultural environment, globalization, graphic symbols, international economic relations, international business, symbolism.

Introduction

In the context of global interdependence deepening and national economies intertwining, the importance of a particular country or region cultural environment is also increasing. This is especially noticeable in the field of international economic relations and business, since, operating in different countries of the world, companies face diverse cultural contexts, which requires the so-called “cultural sensitivity and tolerance” [6, p. 101].

A large number of modern experts focus attention on issues of cross-cultural management, empathetic leadership, cultural intelligence, diversity and inclusion, which along with questions of gender, race and ethnicity now include different aspects of a person such as diverse religious and political beliefs, education, socioeconomic background, sexual orientation, personality, ability, personal characteristics and stages of life, cultural background and even disabilities [7, 12]. Among international companies that have successfully implemented such a concept of cultural diversity and inclusion, Nike, P&G, Coca-Cola, and McDonald’s are known in particular [7, 26]. A Boston Consulting Group study found that companies with more diverse management teams have 19% higher revenues due to innovation [17]. McKinsey research revealed that companies that manage culture effectively in their integration planning are around 50% more likely to capture cost and revenue synergies [23]. Global collaboration has become a significant aspect for businesses success and this cannot occur if businesses do not have the resources, knowledge, and talents of cultural intelligence [26].

And this concerns competent cultural interaction both with employees and with consumers, potential partners, suppliers, stakeholders from different countries, primarily in the context of diplomacy, management and communication. This requires a deep awareness of a whole range of cultural features, nuances and details, including the perception and interpretation of symbols.

The importance of culture as a factor of international business environment is particularly meaningful in the context of its complexity, invisibility and significant impact on another environmental areas. In particular, as emphasized by D. C. Thomas and M. F. Peterson, “the economic, legal, and political characteristics of a country are a manifestation of a nation’s culture” [24]. There are many interpretations of the term “culture”, for example, G. P. Ferraro defines it as “everything that people have, think, and do as members of their society” [8]; G. Hofstede as “collective programming of the mind” or “a system of values” [10]; J. W. Berry, Y. H. Poortinga, M. H. Segall, P. R. Dasen as “the shared way of life of a group of people” [5], A. Phillips as “an accumulation of the beliefs, traditions, language and values of a particular group of people” [21].

At the same time, religion, language, education, material culture, social institutions, aesthetics [5, 6, 9, 11, 24, 25] are the most common elements of the study of international business cultural environment. However, the perception and interpretation of symbols is an equally important category for understanding the specifics of the cultural environment of a particular country or society. As stressed by C. Kluckhohn, “culture

consists in patterned ways of thinking, feeling, and reacting, acquired and transmitted mainly by symbols, constituting the distinctive achievements of human groups, including their embodiment in artifacts" [16].

Analysis of recent research and publications

The importance of culture is widely disclosed in many educational and scientific publications, covering the issue of its role as a component of international business environment, cross-cultural management and psychology, as a principle of building effective cross-cultural teams and workplaces and prevent conflicts, including the works of such authors as G. Hofstede, E. Meyer, G. P. Ferraro, L. Ting, A. J. Ali, L. Yan, R. Holcomb, D. C. Thomas, M. F. Peterson, J. W. Berry, Y. H. Poortinga, M. H. Segall, P. R. Dasen, Y. Yehia, et al.

The discovering of the meaning of symbols as a component of culture and psychology was reflected in many scientists' researches, including the interpretation of archetypes as a collective unconscious by C. G. Jung, the identification of the role of visual and other symbols in the cultural humanity space by R. Addams, O. Boyko, T. I. Kireeva, O. G. Kireeva, M. Manolache, A. Phillips, V. Pylypiv, etc.

The purpose of the study is to identify the role of symbols (especially graphic symbols) in the cultural environment of modern international economic relations and business communication.

Results

As a research object symbol is of interdisciplinary significance, being at the intersection of such fields as history, philosophy, art, cultural studies, psychology, linguistics, semiotics, economics, etc. From the economics point of view, in particular in the context of international economic relations and business, they are primarily the object of the socio-cultural environment research. Some authors claim that "symbols are the basis of culture" [22] and are "called to create and communicate values and traditions to the cultural group" [21], to "express specific ideologies and social standards of the culture that are communicated amongst the group, reflecting the values, beliefs, and identity of a society" [18]. A symbol may be defined as "a universal phenomenon that expresses, preserves, and transmits ideas and values that are essential for the development and functioning of culture in a sensory-receptive form" [3].

In general, symbols are a broad category and can include such concepts as objects, colors, shapes, marks, drawings, gestures, actions, words, sounds or signs that stand for certain meanings, which mostly perform a cultural and communicative function. We all communicate with each other appealing to the symbols (words, gestures, texts, sounds, signs, actions). In the general sense, a symbol is a conventional sign, a universally recognizable aesthetic feature. The structure of the symbol (object image and deep meaning) "is aimed at recreating a complete image of the world through a separate phenomenon" [15]. It is everything that conveys meaning and causes the same social reaction.

In terms of their functionality and structure, symbols are an extremely complex phenomenon, dialectically combining material and immaterial, concrete and

abstract, individual and general, obvious and hidden. Symbolism has a wide interpretive and creative function, generating subjective images of objective reality. Symbols are able to provide a meaningful way of expressing not only knowledge and ideas, but also "feelings, intuitive insights, mystical experience, they are able to influence both rational reflection and the sensory-emotional level" [3]. A symbol is both an image and a sign. Linguistic signs (sign system) and non-linguistic signs (copy signs, symbols) are distinguished. Signs and symbols are something concrete (object, image), something that has its own particular meaning and, at the same time, reflects something general, abstract (concept, idea, hypothesis, concept). Signs and symbols embody a visual image and are used "to reveal the most significant, ancient meaning, for example, the ancient Greek theatrical mask as a symbol of modern stage art" [15].

In general, next types of symbols can be distinguished:

- verbal - words, sounds, language and speech;
- non-verbal - gestures, eye contact, tactile communication, para-language (tone, speed, emphasis, pause), body language, movements, dances, non-verbal signs-indicators (facial expression, tears, laughter - expression of emotions, feelings);
 - natural - objects or phenomena of nature: plants, animals, insects, birds, minerals, etc., natural signs-indicators (weather signs, animal tracks, smoke sign);
 - artificial - numbers, mathematical symbols, musical notes, letters, hieroglyphs, pieces of art, etc.;
 - iconic / specific - portraits, photographs, geographical maps, casts, impressions, traces, models, etc.);
 - conventional / abstract - traffic lights and signs, indices, cartographic signs, coats of arms, emblems, diagrams, graphics, technical schemes, trademarks, quality marks, etc.;
 - functional and status - clothes, houses, interior, cars;
 - ethnic and mythical - Druid symbols, ancient Scandinavian, Greek, Egyptian, Indian, Slavic symbols;
 - religious - Christian, pagan, Buddhist symbols;
 - occult - Tarot, alchemical, zodiac symbols;
 - artistic - artworks, architecture, music;
 - representative - state, political, professional, educational, Olympic, gender, LGBT, heraldic symbols;
 - audio - intangible items in sound, non-graphic form (songs, music, hymns, titles, names, etc.);
 - graphic - drawn symbols (pictures, icons, hieroglyphs, letters, numbers, musical notes, etc.).

Namely graphic symbols or sign systems of writing and images are of particular interest within the framework of this study. According to anthropologists, they are secondary to verbal and non-verbal, arose with the appearance of writing and are a sign of civilizational development. It is not surprising that today we live in an era of high-quality information diversity and an increasing flow of graphic symbols, given the influence of social networks (Instagram, Facebook, Tik-Tok), which create a new format of the world perception. In the modern information society, such phenomena of a

meaningful order as symbols acquire special significance. Today, “the cultural language of mankind includes more and more visual forms of communication” [22]. Symbols are better remembered and at the same time speed up the transmission of messages.

A graphic symbol is a visual embodiment of a word, idea, concept, sound, a specific type of image that has a form, the content of which reveals the characteristic features of a specific visual object, information about its properties, and/or the more significant content of an abstract idea. It is based on the image of the object being depicted.

Acting as an artifact of culture, graphic symbols also perform an anthropological, metalinguistic, communicative function, allowing participants to communicate across time and space. For example, numerous cave paintings found in many parts of the world reveal scenes of the daily life of ancient peoples, including the processes of cattle grazing, gathering, farming, ritual ceremonies, battles, games, celebrations, etc. In general, in ancient civilizations, symbols were often imbued with spiritual or religious significance. Symbolic representation has been inherent in humanity throughout history. These symbols were integral to cultural identity and were woven into various forms of art, such as sculptures, pottery, and murals [18]. Different clans and tribes used their own symbols to decorate flags, shields and clothes. Thus, the symbol unites single things into a certain integrity, fixing it in the cultural code and transmitting it to the next generations [22].

It is obvious that the meanings of symbols really exist only within the limits of human communication, but their perception, interpretation and application may differ depending on the cultural affiliation, which is associated with different experiences and ideas about some of them. They record the social statuses of individuals, and are also an expression of social ties and relationships, and the decoding of the symbol involves knowledge in accordance with the ideological and worldview context accepted in a certain culture, within the framework of which the individual undergoes socialization. On the one hand, it promotes a sense of belonging and cultural uniqueness, and on the other hand, it can cause cross-cultural misunderstanding. In the process of intercultural communication, there is always a risk that its participants may attach different meanings to the same symbol.

For example, as a symbol of power and authority in many European and Western countries an eagle is used, while in many Asian countries - a dragon; on the flags of mainly European countries, a cross is used as a Christian symbol, and on the flags of Islamic countries - a symbol of a crescent and one or more stars. There are examples of negative perception of certain symbols in different countries, for example, violet in Greece is interpreted as a symbol of death, a pig or a dog is a symbol of impurity among Muslims, the cross, as well as the letter “t” in some typefaces may be undesirable for representatives of non-Christian religions. Nazi symbols (swastika) and depictions of body parts should also not be used to avoid cross-cultural misunderstand-

ings. In a cross-cultural context, one should also remember that colors have different meanings in different countries. For example, in Western countries white is considered the color of purity and peace, but in some parts of Asia it is the color of mourning, like purple in most Latin American countries, dark red in Ivory Coast, blue in China, yellow in Syria etc.

In general, the science of symbols (symbolism, semiotics, semiology) is quite complex and, intertwined with many issues of history, philosophy, psychology, etc., constantly seeking answers to the questions of the coding process using sign systems of visual images, alternative interpretations of symbols, putting forward assumptions about why there are similar symbols in different parts of the world, why one symbol has several interpretations. Symbolic thinking has a universal and specific meaning, “universal - because it goes beyond the boundaries of a certain culture, and specific - because it belongs to a certain period of history” [15].

In connection with globalization, widespread information exchange and the increasingly unified communication space of the Internet and social networks, more and more symbols appear in the modern world, which are recognized and understood by millions of people around the world. Exactly through such symbols people with different languages and cultures can form a semantic space in which it will be easier to find mutual understanding, serving as a “visual language that transcends linguistic barriers, connecting believers across time and space” [18]. Primarily due to their simple and accessible forms, such symbols are perceived intuitively, appeal to the human subconscious and form a universal language understood by people from all over the world. In this connection, they are part of what C. G. Jung called “collective unconscious” or “patterns of instinctual behavior” [14, p. 44].

Among such universal symbols, the following are particularly well-known: Heart Symbol (♥) - iconic representation of love and affection, emotions related to love, friendship, and compassion; Peace Symbol (☸) - peace and anti-war movements; Yin-Yang Symbol (☯) - dynamic balance and harmony present in the natural world; Cross Symbol (†) - Christianity, crucifixion, hope, redemption, and sacrifice; Star of David (✡) / Magen David - Jewish identity and heritage [2, 18] and a large number of similar ones.

And there is an extremely large number of such symbols. We meet them everywhere in our daily life: on traffic, stations, airports, supermarkets, exchange points signs, in public toilets and transport, we notice them on the passers-by tattoos and clothes, on flags, cars, smartphones and other appliances, on geographical and playing cards, in various digital applications and modern means of communication through messengers and social networks, including the use of emojis, emoticons, stickers, GIFs, memes. Some of these symbols are more common and used in many areas of human activity and communication, including international business.

Speaking of universal symbols that can have a direct impact on the cultural and communicative aspect of international economic relations and business, the following categories can be outlined:

1) Universal coded character set (UCS) - a standard set of symbols defined by the International Standard ISO / IEC 10646, which is the basis of many character encodings. The latest version contains over 136,000 abstract symbols, each identified by a unique name and an integer called a code point [13]. These symbols are designed to serve communication in many areas of human activity, including production, technological processes, trade, transportation, etc.;

2) The Unicode character set, which is supported jointly with the UCS standard, ISO / IEC 10646 and has an identical code system. It is an industry standard designed to provide digital representation of characters from all world scripts and special characters. The Unicode Consortium is the standards body for the internationalization of software and services. Deployed on more than 20 billion devices around the world, Unicode also provides the solution for internationalization and the architecture to support localization [1]. It is a non-profit organization supported by Apple, Google, Facebook, Adobe and other major technology companies;

3) Emojis are symbols, in turn, taken from the universal symbol library of the Unicode Consortium, which today represent a repository of 180 symbols. Although the emoji has a long and ambiguous history of origin, with its invention attributed to such authors as V. Nabokov, A. Bierce, A. Lincoln, J. Gutenberg, H. Zapf, Ch. Bigelow, & K. Holmes, the technical groundwork for emoji was originally laid in 1999 by Sh. Kurita, who worked for the Japanese mobile phone company DoCoMo [4];

4) Logotypes of commercial, non-commercial, political, governmental, non-governmental, international organizations. At the same time, commercial logos play the role of an element of the company's corporate style and image, act as a visual image market component that occupies a central place in the company's individuality, reflects its philosophy and general vector, creates a first impression in the audience and, along with communicative, performs such functions as mnemonic, perceptual, synesthetic and fractal [20]. Symbolic languages of the worlds of technology, law, games, and sports can turn symbolic meaning into a brand thanks to a graphic identity that is built on a symbol of one of these subcultures [22]. Due to the harmonious application of biomimicry methods and such components as shape, color, font, which is able to make the logo more understandable already at the subconscious level, that is, to universalize or internationalize its perception, it is able to perform the role of a ready-made memory block, filled with associative and motivational content, additional sensory qualities, mechanisms of creating a complete image [20];

5) Countries and cities flags and coats of arms are legally defined symbols of state sovereignty, created taking into account the study of historical legends and annals, heraldry of national rulers and territories and/or the modern economic, political and social situation of the state. Such symbols are used to identify different countries, regions, cities, organizations;

6) Symbols of foreign currencies are primarily independent graphemes, different from the letters that

begin the name of the corresponding monetary unit, which arose or were built on the basis of individual letters of the Cyrillic or Latin alphabet, used for the shortest and at the same time unique (excellent from other monetary units) currency designation. In the Unicode standard, the section dedicated to currencies is called "Currency Symbols".

The above groups of symbols are designed to universalize and simplify the process of communication at the global level, aimed at facilitating the search for ways to identify international subjects, objects and processes. In particular, the last three categories of symbols generally help to denote subjects of international economic relations at the micro, meta, and macro levels: from firms, companies, enterprises, political, governmental, non-governmental structures to cities, states, and international organizations. The last two categories of symbols represent the concept of national sovereignty, encoding a message about the state and economic, currency policy of individual countries. The interdependence between the mentioned groups of symbols is also obvious, in particular, emojis and Unicode symbols are based on the universal international base of standard symbols UCS, ISO, which also includes symbols of national flags and currencies. Commercial logos often use patterns or elements of standard symbols. Thus, in addition to the intuitive comprehensibility of the most common symbols in the world, their universal interpretation is ensured due to the existence and development of such international bases of standard symbols, which creates the basis of a global communication culture.

Conclusions

Therefore, the perception and interpretation of symbols is an important research direction regarding the cultural environment of international economic relations and business and includes such concepts as objects, colors, shapes, marks, drawings, gestures, actions, words, sounds or signs and such types of symbols as verbal and non-verbal, natural and artificial, iconic and conventional, functional and status, ethnic and mythical, audio and graphic. However, today graphic symbols play a special role, performing a global, universal cultural and communicative function, filling the digital information flow between people from different countries with a special compact content, opening a space for their common interpretation. The basic role in the cultural-communicative sphere of modern international economic relations and business is played by globally standardized and generally accepted categories of symbols, which, along with intuitive perception, are designed to convey the same meanings, knowledge, ideas, feelings, emotions, performing a metalinguistic, communicative function on a global scale.

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